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ORDP: OPEN RESEARCH DATA PILOT

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Abbreviation

DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
OA	Open Access
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot

Executive Summary

AURORAL is part of the EC's Open Research Data Pilot programme; therefore, the goal of this deliverable is to specify the terms for the project participation in that programme. As such, this deliverable presents the AURORAL Open Research Data Strategy and explains how AURORAL aims to provide open access to the publications and data generated by the project.

The AURORAL open research data strategy is in line with the H2020 guidelines. Furthermore, the AURORAL Zenodo community will be the entry point for all the AURORAL open publications and data.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

In line with the principles of open access to research data and publications generated through H2020 programmes, the project AURORAL participates in the Open Research Data Pilot carried out by the European Commission. As such, a Data Management Plan (DMP) has been created to deal with the data collected and generated during the project. This deliverable presents the open access strategy of AURORAL, both for publications and datasets.

1.2. Relation to other project work

The open research data strategy is part of the overall management strategy of the AURORAL project. It affects the work of all work packages of the project and has tight relationships with the quality assurance plan (AURORAL_D1.5) and with the Data Management Plan (AURORAL_D1.8).

1.3. Structure of the document

This document is structured as follows. In chapter 2, the AURORAL open research data strategy for scientific publications and research data is presented, introducing the AURORAL community in Zenodo as the entry point for all the open publications and data. Chapters 3 and 4 present detailed steps to be followed in the case of scientific publications and research data, respectively. Finally, chapter 5 presents the conclusions and the next steps that will be followed.

2. Open access strategy

Open access (OA) refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and reusable [1]. 'Scientific' refers to all academic disciplines. In the context of research and innovation, 'scientific information' can mean:

1. peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals) or
2. research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).

The AURORAL Grant Agreement already provides the grounds for the open access strategy of the project, as described next, which are aligned with the EC Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020 [1].

2.1. Scientific publications

Each beneficiary ensures open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

In particular:

- a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications.

Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

- b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
 - i. on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - ii. within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
- c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

2.2. Research data

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action ('data'), the beneficiaries must:

- a) deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:

- i. the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible;
 - ii. other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan';
- b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

This does not change the obligation to protect results, the confidentiality obligations, the security obligations or the obligations to protect personal data, as described in the Grant Agreement, all of which still apply.

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data under Point (a)(i) and (ii), if the achievement of the action's main objective would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.

2.3. The AURORAL community in Zenodo

The AURORAL community in Zenodo [2] will be the entry point for all the open publications and data in the project. Zenodo is a repository promoted by CERN and OpenAIRE that provides the means to develop the AURORAL open strategy.

Some of the benefits of using Zenodo as a repository are the following:

- It enables the preservation of open assets, including the persistence of metadata and data, and the definition of different preservation policies and plans.
- Defines Persistent and Unique Identifiers for open assets, which enable data identification, discovery, retrieval and versioning.
- Allows defining machine-readable metadata for open assets, which enables finding and referencing to data, using metadata standards that are broadly accepted.
- Provides data access, enabling access to data under well-specified conditions, ensuring data authenticity and integrity and providing information about licensing and permissions (ideally in machine-readable form).

3. Open access to scientific publications

AURORAL will provide open access to all its peer-reviewed scientific publications. This includes journal articles and other types of publications such as monographs, books, conference proceedings, or grey literature (informally published written material not controlled by scientific publishers, e.g., reports).

In order to ensure open access to the project scientific publications, these steps will be followed:

1. To deposit the publication in the AURORAL community of Zenodo.
2. To provide open access to the publication.

3.1. Depositing publications in Zenodo

Beneficiaries must deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in the AURORAL community of Zenodo. This must be done as soon as possible and at the latest upon publication.

This step applies even where open access publishing ('gold' open access) is chosen to ensure that the article is preserved in the long term.

'Machine-readable electronic copy' - publications must be in a format that can be used and understood by a computer. They must be stored in text file formats that are either standardised or otherwise publicly known so that anyone can develop new tools for working with the documents.

In some cases, the final version of an article can be deposited before publication, for example at the time when the article is accepted by the journal. The latest acceptable time to deposit a publication is the date of publication.

Where possible, the version deposited should be identical to the published version (in layout, pagination, etc.).

Beneficiaries must aim to deposit at the same time as the publication the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications ('underlying data'), as described below.

3.2. Providing open access to publications

After depositing publications, beneficiaries must ensure open access to those publications. To do so, beneficiaries can choose one of two main ways to meet this requirement:

- a) **Self-archiving / 'green' OA:** once the publication is deposited in Zenodo, beneficiaries must ensure open access to the publication within at most 6 months.
- b) **Open access publishing / 'gold' OA:** researchers can also publish in open access journals, or in hybrid journals that both sell subscriptions and offer the option of making individual articles openly accessible.

Beneficiaries must also provide open access, through the repository, to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. These must be in a standard format and must include:

- terms ["European Union (EU)" & "Horizon 2020"]
- name of the action, acronym and grant number
- publication date, the length of the embargo period (if applicable) and a persistent identifier.

4. Open access to research data

AURORAL will provide open access to all its research data that qualifies to be open. This includes:

- the 'underlying data' (the data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications), including the associated metadata (i.e., metadata describing the research data deposited), as soon as possible
- any other data (for instance curated data not directly attributable to a publication, or raw data), including the associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the DMP – that is, according to the individual judgement by each project/grantee.

In order to ensure open access to the project research data, these steps will be followed:

1. To deposit the data in the AURORAL community of Zenodo.
2. To provide open access to the data.

4.1. Depositing data in Zenodo

Beneficiaries must deposit the project research datasets in the AURORAL community of Zenodo as soon as possible.

These datasets should follow the FAIR principles: research data should be findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. This makes sure that the data is well formatted in order to exploit the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data, in addition to supporting its reuse by stakeholders [3]. According to the FAIR principles, data should be:

- identified in a persistent manner;
- properly described with enough metadata;
- stored so that both humans and machines can easily access it;
- well structured so that it might be integrated with other data sets;
- clearly presents well-defined a license or terms of use.

4.2. Providing open access to data

After depositing datasets, beneficiaries must ensure open access to those datasets, enabling third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) this research data.

At the same time, projects should provide information via the chosen repository about the tools available to the beneficiaries that are needed to validate the results, e.g., specialized software or software code, algorithms and analysis protocols. Where possible, they should provide these instruments themselves.

5. Conclusions

This deliverable presents the open research data strategy of the AURORAL project, which is aligned with the rest of the management activities in the project, specifically with the quality assurance plan (which defines the quality procedure previous to the opening of research publications and data) and with the data management plan (which defines how the open data of the project will be managed).

Therefore, this open research data strategy complements both the quality assurance plan and with the data management plan and supports the project partners in opening their research outputs (either publications or data) when needed.

During the project lifetime, the strategy defined in this deliverable will be applied and the AURORAL Zenodo community will be the entry point for all the AURORAL open publications and data. Using Zenodo as repository will allow maintaining collaboratively the open research outputs of the project.

6. References

- [1] European Commission. Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020. Version 3.2. 21 March 2017.
- [2] AURORAL community in Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/communities/auroral/>, retrieved 2021-03-26
- [3] Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>